

ISic3170

I.Sicily inscription 3170

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Church of S. Giovanni, i.e. catacomb)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di San Giovanni

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329747

1. [έν]θάδε κίτε Γ.3-4. -
2. [.1-2.]ία ή καλής μνήμη[ς],
3. [τ]ελευτήσασα έτ[ών — —].
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645500

PHI 329747

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 15.0587

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 259 no.1 dr

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